

A MODEL FOR PREDICTING FREE SURFACE FLOW OF THE RTM PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

A novel model is developed for modelling the Resin Transfer Moulding process. The compressible two-phase flow porous media formulations accounting for the capillary effects and relative permeability are derived. The resulting equations lead to a non-linear coupled closed system that contains a parabolic mixture pressure equation plus a convection-diffusion-reaction saturation equation. Then a staggered Galerkin finite element approach is used to decouple the solution of mixture pressure and saturation degree. Moreover, the Streamline-Upwind/Petrov-Galerkin (SUPG) technique is applied to attenuate the oscillations on the saturation solutions. The model accuracy and convergence of the solving scheme is then demonstrated through 1-D numerical examples. The present model is turned out to be a standard boundary value and initial value problem with high computational efficiency and robust solutions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Either pre-impregnated plies (prepregs) or Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI) of dry fibre composite preform are widely used to produce composite laminates and components in now days. Thanks to high toughness miscible resins dispersed and bounded around fabric architecture, it gives the prepreg composites superior mechanical performance; but also leads to drawbacks such as the expensive manufacturing costs, weak formability and limited product life. As the development of the composite material manufacturing technologies, the resin infusion processes like Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process are likely to be exploited and improve the implementation and economic viability of composite materials in different industrials, e.g. automotive and aerospace structures [1-3]. In this context, Lim and Lee [4] and Serge Abrate [5] reported simulations on resin flow in fibre preforms. In those studies, they assume the resin is incompressible and neglect the capillary effects and relative permeability, generally leading to an inaccurate prediction of pressure and saturation rate at the flow front. Likewise, Larsson et al. [6] extended the research scope and reported a mathematical model that totally kept in line with the Theory of Porous Media (TPM), and was established based on the continuum mechanics framework.

We propose herein a novel TPM approach to model the resin free surface flow. A linear mixture pressure assumption is made to substitute the intrinsic pressure of each phase as unknown; at the same time, capillary effects and relative permeability are considered. Another aim of the present research is to derive a formulation that can handle various cases of the RTM process and simultaneously be efficiently numerically solved. To this end, two coupled equations – a pressure equation and a saturation equation - are derived. In addition, a staggered approach is employed to handle the coupling between mixture pressure and the saturation degree. However, at the flow front, problems arise with a numerically induced oscillating behaviour on the solution of saturation degree. This is due to that the saturation equation reveals a convection-diffusion-reaction style. In order to stabilize solutions, a (SUPG) stabilization technique by Hughes and Brooks [7] is used to add an artificial diffusivity to the original weak formulation to smoothen the solution.

2 GOVERNING EQUATIONS

2.1 Preliminaries and governing equations

To set the stage, the fibre mat during resin infusion is considered as a porous material preform with pore spaces that are either filled by liquid resin or contains only gas (or vacuum). We are thereby led to consider the problem as a partially to fully fluid-saturated solid within the region B (Fig. 1). Typically, the fluid front separates the liquid-saturated and unsaturated regions as depicted in Fig. 1. For both regions the solid and fluid phases are considered homogenized in terms of volume fractions n^s and n^f connected via the saturation constraint

$$n^s + n^f = 1 \quad (1)$$

where $n^s = \frac{V^s}{V}$, and $n^f = \frac{V^f}{V}$. V^s (V^f , resp.) is the volume portion of the solid (fluid, resp.) respect to a control volume V .

Figure 1: Solid in reference and spatial configurations represent resin infusion of a fibre mat with fully-saturated and unsaturated regions at the left and right side of the fluid infusion process zone (in grey region), respectively. The process zone is migrating in the material.

To describe the partial saturation, we consider the fluid phase as a mixture of an incompressible liquid constituent and a compressible gas constituent. The fluid phase volume fraction n^f is further subdivided into liquid φ^l and gas φ^g volume fractions defined as

$$n^f = \psi^l + \psi^g \quad (2)$$

We thus conclude that the unsaturated region of B is just the special case when the fluid volume fraction consists of completely unfilled pore spaces, i.e. $n^f \rightarrow \psi^g$. The fluid phase mixture may be further described upon introducing the *degree of liquid saturation*, ξ , ($0 \leq \xi \leq 1$), defining the liquid volume fraction φ^l in terms of the fluid volume fraction n^f as $\psi^l = \xi n^f$ (and for gas phase, $\psi^g = (1 - \xi)n^f$). Clearly, $\xi = 0$ corresponds to completely gas-filled pores and $\xi = 1$ represents fully liquid-saturated medium. As to the solid phase of the partially fluid-saturated continuum, incompressibility is assumed for the solid $\alpha = s$, whereas the fluid phase $\alpha = f$ is generally considered as compressible.

Based on the *kinematics* of phases continuum and concerning the *homogenized two phase mixture* in unsaturated conditions we may establish the balance of mass as

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}^s + \left(\frac{\rho^l - \rho^g}{\rho^f} \dot{\xi} + \frac{1 - \xi}{\rho^f} \dot{\rho}^g \right) n^f + \frac{1}{\rho^f} \nabla \cdot (n^f \rho^f \mathbf{v}^{rf}) = 0 \quad (3)$$

We also include the mass balance considering the liquid phase solely, in [6], written as

$$n^f \dot{\xi} + \xi \frac{\dot{j}}{j} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}^l = 0 \quad (4)$$

From the homogenization, the relative fluid velocity \mathbf{v}^{rf} is obtained as

$$\mathbf{v}^{rf} = \frac{1}{\rho^f} (\xi \rho^l \mathbf{v}^{rl} + (1 - \xi) \rho^g \mathbf{v}^{rg}) \quad (5)$$

where we, in turn, postulate the phase intrinsic velocity in terms of local Darcy flow law based on a representation of the capillary pressure cf. [10]. This yields

$$\mathbf{v}^l = -\frac{\hat{k} k_{rl}}{\mu_l} \nabla p^l = -K^l \nabla p^l = -K^l \left(\nabla p + \left(1 - (1 - \xi) \log' (p_c(\xi)) \right) p_c(\xi) \nabla \xi \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{v}^g = -\frac{\hat{k} k_{rg}}{\mu_g} \nabla p^g = -K^g \left(\nabla p + \left(1 + \xi \log' (p_c(\xi)) \right) p_c(\xi) \nabla \xi \right) \quad (7)$$

In (6) and (7), \hat{k} is the absolute permeability suggested by Kozeny and Carman [8]; $k_{r\alpha}$ ($\alpha = l$ or g) denotes the relative permeability in [9]. p_c illustrates the capillary pressure depending on the saturation. To simply the express, let K^l and K^g stand for a terms of permeability of phases transportation in the mixture sense.

2.2 Weak form and numerics

In terms of the pressure equation (3) and the saturation equation (4), the consequent weak forms are obtained in the reference configuration as:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{B_0} \eta \rho^f \dot{J} d\Omega + \int_{B_0} \eta n^f \mathcal{J} \left((\rho^l - \rho^g) \dot{\xi} + (1 - \xi) \rho^g \dot{\rho}^g \right) d\Omega - \int_{B_0} \nabla \eta n^f \rho^f \mathcal{J} \cdot \mathbf{v}^{rf} d\Omega \\ = \int_{\Gamma_0} \eta Q d\Gamma, \forall \eta \in P \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{B_0} \chi n^f \mathcal{J} \dot{\xi} d\Omega + \int_{B_0} \chi \xi \dot{J} d\Omega - \int_{B_0} \nabla \chi n^f \xi \rho^f \mathcal{J} \cdot \mathbf{v}^{rl} d\Omega \\ = \int_{\Gamma_0} \chi H d\Gamma, \forall \chi \in S \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In above weak forms, the P and S are the spaces of test functions, η and χ , which are multiplied to (3) and (4) respectively. The Q and H are fluxes determined by boundary conditions.

Being pertinent to the standard Galerkin procedure, we note that both the mixture pressure $p(x, t)$ and the saturation degree field $\xi(x, t)$ are FE-represented. In particular, the ξ field involves gradients due to the representation of the capillary pressure.

A specially designed penalty method is employed to tackle the problem in the limits $0 \leq \xi \leq 1$. Moreover, to handle the extreme sensitivity in the temporal response a SUPG stabilization is employed. The sensitivity is manifested by that we need a very small time step to obtain a stable solution, free from severe oscillations. To this end, we characterize the influence of convective and diffusive effects by the Péclet number $P_e = (|\mathbf{a}|_2 h) / 2\mathbf{v}$, which shows the relative importance of convection domination. In our case the \mathbf{a} vector comprises $\mathbf{a}_p = \partial_\xi K^l \nabla p$ and $\mathbf{a}_\xi = \partial_\xi \bar{K}^l \nabla \xi$; the diffusive term \mathbf{v} represents as \bar{K}^l , where $\bar{K}^l = K^l (p^c - (1 - \xi) p_\xi^c)$. By following the concepts in [7, 11-15], we can reformulate the weak form (9) to a stabilized fashion. From our numerical simulations it is our experience that the Péclet number can be as high as 1×10^{10} when the diffusive term is extremely small. Hence, the stabilization effect to the SUPG is significant in our problem to improve the computational efficiency.

4 NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

Firstly, we consider a resin infusion problem in one space dimension. The fibre layups preform is one meter long, and the resin is injected from left inlet and outlets from the other end. The porous domain and liquid material parameters are given in Table 1.

Parameters	Unit	Identification	Value
n^f	–	Porosity	0.35
\hat{k}	–	absolute permeability	2.537×10^{-9}
ρ_l	[kg/m ³]	resin density	1000
μ_l	[pa s]	resin viscosity	2.7
μ_g	[pa s]	gas viscosity	1.983×10^{-5}
n_b	–	capillary pressure constant	1.9
p_e	[MPa]	entry pressure	0.02 or 0

Table 1: Material parameters.

A preliminary analytical solution is developed as a reference. From the material balance equation at the flow front we have, $v_l|_{\text{at flow front}} = n^f (1.0 - \xi_{\text{initial}}) \frac{dx}{dt}$. By inserting the Richard equation of liquid phase, we have: $-k_r \frac{\hat{k}}{\mu_l} \frac{dp_l}{dx} = n^f (1.0 - \xi_{\text{initial}}) \frac{dx}{dt}$. Now let's assume that the gradient of pressure $\frac{dp_l}{dx} = -\frac{p}{x}$ that is a constant in the saturation developed zone and equals to zeros at the non-saturated zone. The above equation can be finally simplified as,

$$k_r \frac{\hat{k}}{\mu_l} \frac{p}{x} = n^f (1.0 - \xi_{\text{initial}}) \frac{dx}{dt} \quad (10)$$

where $k_r = \int_0^1 \xi^{3+\frac{2}{n_b}} d\xi$ denotes a factor to represent the process of saturation developing from zero to one at the flow front. Finally the global saturation $\bar{\xi} = x/L$ can be solved from (10), which is expressed as,

$$x = \frac{\sqrt{2(\hat{k} p t + 5 \times 10^{-7} \mu_l n^f)}}{\sqrt{\mu_l n^f}} \quad (11)$$

The (8) and (9) are solved with the boundary conditions below for the purpose of simulating resin infusion process, $\xi(0, t) = 0.001$, $p(0, t) = 4$ MPa, $p(1, t) = 0.05$ MPa, $\partial_x \xi(1, t) = 0$. And the initial values are given by $\xi(x, 0) = 1.0$, $p(x, 0) = 0.05$ MPa.

The plots (in Fig. 2) show the mixture pressure and saturation development after 1.5 seconds infusion. In the case of ignoring capillary effect, the mixture pressure is same as the phase pressure - liquid (resin) pressure and gas pressure. Instead, when the capillary pressure is considered, the wetting phase (resin) pressure will deviate dramatically from the mixture pressure, but the non-wetting phase (gas) pressure is almost in line with mixture pressure. One more thing can be observed from Fig. 2 is that the effect of capillary pressure can influence the saturation development speed, the higher capillary pressure the faster development speed. Apart from pressure response, the saturation curves behave as a "L" shape, which implies that the processing zone (the region between unsaturated and full saturated) given by the new model consist with the practical observation - the resin flow front locates in vicinity of the interface between non-saturated and full saturated regions.

Figure 2: Two numerical example cases results at 1.5 second. The left hand side two figures show the case when capillary pressure is disabled; whilst the right side figures represent the effects from capillary pressure. In the plots, p denotes the mixture pressure, p_l is the pressure of liquid (resin) phase and p_g represents gas phase pressure.

The mesh and time step sensitivity studies are carried out to concern the convergence of solutions under different spatial and time discretization. For the mesh sensitivity study, a coarse mesh (100 elements), a fine mesh (300 elements) and the 1000 elements very fine mesh are considered herein. In Fig. 3, it shows that the global saturation $\bar{\xi}$ from all of these three meshes convergence very well. At the same time, the time step sensitivity analysis tells that the solution starts to converge when the time discretization $\Delta t = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ s is chosen.

Figure 3: The mesh convergence study (left) and time step sensitivity analysis (right).

Figure 4: Convergence error of different meshes and time discretization respect to the finest mesh and time step. Solid and dash lines plot the results obtained with SUPG activated, whilst the dot line illustrates the case when SUPG is deactivated.

In Fig .4, the mesh size refinement contributes very little to the error reduction, however, the convergence highly relates to the time step setting. Besides, the convergence rate when the SUPG is activated is higher than the case without SUPG. This also implies that the implementation of SUPG in this problem is important.

Finally a comparison between the new model, old model [6] and analytical solution is made. Since in the analytical solution, the assumption on the pressure gradient is proposed, it implies there is difference between the present model and analytical results. But one can notice that, from Fig. 2, the pressure curve is very close to the assumption, in other words, the difference should be small as well. The above analysis can be verified in Fig. 5. The solution of new model lies closely to the analytical solution but the model [6] deviates far away from it. The bars in the figure represent the root-mean-square errors, which suggests that the new model gives a more accurate solution of resin infusion processing.

Figure 5: The comparison on the global saturation degree between analytical solution, the present model and the reference model [6]. The bars in the figure illustrate the root-mean-square errors against the analytical results.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we established a mathematical model for the RTM process. The model is based on a three-phase porous media theory with the consideration of capillary effects. The model is developed from the continuum mechanics framework which contains kinematic, constitutive and entropy relation and formulations. The saturation evolution concept derived from resin mass balance equation is then used to represent the flow from movement. Within the model, the strong coupled ξ and p are solved by a staggered approach; and in each solver (solve for ξ or p), the standard Petrov - Galerkin finite element method is used to solve equations in conjunction with the SUPG technique to remedy the solution stabilization issues. In general, therefore, the paper models the RTM process to a boundary variable and initial variable problem.

This model is also compared with a simplified analytical solution, and sufficient evidences show the new model gives the acceptable solutions. The numerical example also reveals that the mixture pressure can substitute or can be used to represent the non-wetting phase (gas) pressure, if the capillary effect is weak but exists and the wetting phase are nearly incompressible, as, for instance, in oil-gas system in petroleum industry [16]. Finally the convergence studies confirm the robustness and efficiency of the present model, which implies the model can be used in various RTM process conditions.

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